

Industry 4.0 Conference: The locked potential of BI & HR

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ABSTRACT

In this research we will investigate how the application of business intelligence can contribute to making decisions based on a certain degree of subjectivity. These are decisions that are made in which a decision is made by the decision maker on the basis of their opinion (for example, whether or not someone has passed a driving test). This is the opposite to objective decision-making in which quantitative data forms the basis for a decision (for example, whether or not someone has passed a theoretical final exam). The research focuses on the HR field where the focus is on the decisions in the selection & recruitment process. The existing literature showed that there is certainly a need to be able to support decisions with quantitative data that BI can help with. However, it also seems that recruiters do not want all decisions to depend on the digitization of data, since they also want to continue to influence the decisions themselves.

KEYWORDS

Business Intelligence, HR, Subjective decision making process.

INTRODUCTION

Managing an organisation involves constant decision-making, which in most scenarios is based on intuition, wit and experience (Sayegh, Anthony & Perrewé, 2004). Employing a manager with the required skill set is therefore essential to running a successful business - yet even accomplished managers suffer from occasional lapses in judgement, particularly when a decision is emotional, intuition-based or made under a crisis situation. Unlike other organisational aspects,

subjective decisions have been impossible to automate, with advanced Machine Learning systems being unable to simulate human emotion and intuition (Mosavi, 2013). The solution for an agile and reliable decision-making process may therefore not be automation, rather support for human intuition through Information Technology. Watson & Wixom (2016) suggest adopting Business Intelligence, specifically the data warehousing aspect of it. With these systems, data is moved from multiple source systems into one integrated 'data warehouse', allowing a data warehouse team to "transform it so that it is meaningful for decision support" (Watson & Wixom, 2016).

Recruitment & retention, an aspect of Human Resource Management (HRM) will be taken as a case sample for this study. It provides an organisational decision-making environment representative of this paper's topic, having no universal rules or guidelines to follow due to it being intimate, subjective, and unambiguous between organisations. Furthermore, the idea of implementing technology to reduce the workload of HR in recruitment is not a new one (Bhatia, 2013), providing a context to further build upon. With the rise of IT, opportunities arose to reduce the required time investment in the recruitment process by reallocating workload from HR staff to information systems, e.g. through advanced computerized personality tests. Such automation in recruitment has been imperfect thus far with the inability of machines to adequately distinguish a "good fit" from a "bad fit" by itself (Zhang, L., & Wang, H., 2006).

To elaborate upon the level of intuition required in the recruitment process; recruitment involves an elaborate assessment of a candidate's fit to the company (Jones, D. A., Willness, C., & Macneil, S., 2009). This includes objective facts, e.g. education, past experience, personality tests,

etc., however it also includes personal assessments, for example whether they would get along with the teams, requiring a high interpersonal skill level, as well as an elaborate sense of intuition on the recruiter’s side. Moreover, there is no set rule for hiring employees; no software package can be generalised. Each company and recruiter within has their own idea for an employee. The implications of this subjectivity on the use of BI tools is to be further discussed in this paper.

The ultimate goal of this paper is to provide further insights in the applicability of Business Intelligence on the decision-making processes in organisations, aiming to improve the speed and reliability of intuitive decisions by providing factual, data-driven context. This paper will provide ideas to further increase productivity through the implementation of information systems, and set a foundation for further research into Business Intelligence and its influence on decision-making processes.

Problem statement

Business Intelligence (BI) is used in large numbers of organizations, however the Human Resources (HR) departments have not fully realised its potential, specifically in the selection & recruitment phases. For the selection & recruitment of new employees, HR has a set of criteria that it strictly follows in order to find the best candidates (Timar & Balas, 2007). However the process of finding new candidates takes a great deal of time. This also requires hiring (external) staff to actively search for new employees, therefore organizations have to spend more money on this. The point of a business intelligence system is to transfer raw data to valuable information in order to help companies make decisions (Azeroual & Theel, 2018). Therefore, the hypothesis is that BI should support the selection & recruitment by using an algorithm that is based off the criteria that HR have made. BI solutions could save money for organizations.

From the research papers it is known that business intelligence can aid the subjective decision making in HR. This can be done through the use of dashboards and using an algorithm for finding new candidates. However, for the selection & recruitment process, there are certain activities that are fairly subjective. Meaning, it requires actual human interaction for making decisions, since these are personal activities. It is known that business intelligence can be used to collect data and transform these into decisions. Therefore, this research will focus on whether business intelligence can also contribute to the HR

subjective activities within the selection & recruitment process.

This research is managerially relevant, since HR departments of organizations could potentially save money and time if the research question is answered. Because, HR does not have to spend extra time to manually do the subjective activities. Furthermore, this research is also relevant for the academics related in this field. Since there is a clear knowledge gap whether data warehousing could potentially help in a subjective decision making process. In order to keep this research feasible, the research will conduct a case study about the subject decision making activities in HR. However, this research is generalizable for other decision making processes in several other branches. Therefore, the following research questions follows: ‘How can data warehousing contribute to the subjective decision-making-processes?’

This research will be conducted in a specific case where the subjective decision making processes within the selection and recruitment process will be investigated.

The following sub-questions are formulated to help execute the research:

1. How is Business Intelligence (data warehousing) used for decision making in HR?
2. How are subjective decisions made within selection & recruitment processes?
3. What are the shortcomings of the subjective decision making of the selection & recruitment processes?

Figure 1: Conceptual model

The image above shows what the conceptual model looks like. The term Data warehousing is used to indicate which aspect of BI we will use as an independent variable in the research. The relationship (arrow) between data warehousing and the subjective decision making process is the contribution it can make. The size of the organization plays an important role in this, since

large organizations may need data warehousing more than small organizations due to the fact that large organizations have more data going through the recruitment and selection process due to more vacancies and job applications. Skill level implies how skilled a company is with the use of BI. Whether a company also has experience with BI gives a good indication of the skill level.

The following hypotheses are formulated:

H1: The usage of data warehousing has an added value in the subjective decision making process

H2: Company size influences the relationship between a company and subjective decision making.

H3: Skill level influences the relationship between the use of BI and subjective decision making.

Method

This chapter aims to provide an outline of the research methodology used to answer the questions that were raised in the problem statement. To answer these questions, an insight must be made into the decision-making processes that currently takes place in HR. Once the necessary understanding of these processes is achieved, we can divulge further into what data is required to conceive each of these decisions. Each decision has its own degree of subjectivity; a consideration whether a candidate fits the company culture is of a heavier subjective nature than whether they have the required credentials. Once the perceived degree of subjectivity in these processes is established, this research aims to provide insight whether BI can provide a supportive framework in these decision-making processes.

Firstly, existing literature will be reviewed in order to gain insight into the decision-making processes that currently take place in HR. As it is a long-existing concept, there is no need to take interviews here. Research on the matter has been conducted. Afterwards, once the required knowledge about these processes is acquired, a survey will be conducted among professionals in de HR-industry. This survey will be a mixed method of qualitative and quantitative data collection. Quantitative due to the nature of being a survey, but also qualitative, for we will do an in-depth exploration.

For the survey the online tool *enquetemaken.nu* will be used. The questions have been formed in a way they provide researchers with the necessary data to analyze the research questions, and also whether respondents match the required profile. The sampling method used is snowball sampling, part of the non-probability

sampling methods. The aim of this paper is not to test a hypothesis under a broad population, but to develop an initial understanding. The survey will be conducted among HR professionals in the personal networks of the researchers, consisting of four multiple-choice questions and six open questions. The survey will be sent to approximately 10 people with the sidenote that these people will distribute it within their network (for example colleagues). Consult Appendix A for the design of the survey.

For the discovery of existing HR processes, literature was used from a disclosure of HR5. A consultancy firm that specializes in human resources management.

A content analysis was performed over the returned surveys. Firstly, surveys filled in by anyone not involved in HR decision-making processes were removed from the sample. Secondly, from the surveys a distinction was made between processes that have a high degree of human interaction (or subjectivity) and processes that have a low degree. Lastly, an analysis was made of which processes professionals think a BI solution might have a positive impact on decision-making processes.

Results

HR in organizations use BI that provides for tasks such as: reports, analysis, analysis, dashboards and metrics (Dias & Sousa, 2015). Furthermore, the same article described that BI provides important information for HR that help make decisions for the Human Resource managers. Organizations wishing to improve their capacity, should implement HRMS (Human Resources Management Systems) to strengthen the capacity of an organization. IT is so important for HR, it is also called the backbone of HR functions (Dias & Sousa, 2015). BI helps HR to find better applicants (assets) to increase their competitive advantage. So organizations that want an edge over their competitors, use BI in HR.

New employees are considered important assets within a company. Therefore it is important that HR finds new employees as fast as they can, so that they can have a competitive advantage. Furthermore, BI also provides useful dashboards of employees within an organization (Dias & Sousa, 2015). These dashboards describes the work performance of all employees and can give good insight to the HR department about their employees. Typically the larger organizations have invested more in BI than smaller-sized organizations.

The survey has gathered answers from 16

people (n = 16) in total. Of the 16 participants, roughly 23% percent of them worked in the IT industry, 54% in the logistics industry and 22% worked in other industries that were not included in the survey. Furthermore, 84% of the sample size has mentioned that they do experience a high employee turnover.

69% of the respondents think computerized data (business intelligence) could help them in these decision-making processes. When asked how, most agreed more data could be provided to support these decision-making processes. However, most also acknowledged a degree of subjectivity will always remain.

Out of our respondents, 77% experiences problems or inefficiencies when determining whether a candidate is suited for a position. They report most problems originate when a candidate appears to be different on the job than portrayed in their interview.

Furthermore, the survey revealed that the most participants start making subjective decisions from the first job interview, which can be in the office or through the telephones. Which means that the from the conversation, HR already starts deciding whether a candidate is suitable or not. To the question “In what way do you determine a candidate's fit to a position prior to the interview? Please elaborate your answer.” HR mentioned that they look at the curriculum vitae (CV) and compare these with the criteria of the vacancy. They mentioned that they are strict when it comes to picking out CVs, since they just compare it with demands that are written in the vacancy. Furthermore, a small amount mentioned that motivation is also important. Besides their knowledge and competences, motivation is also a point where HR looks at.

To the question: “In what way do you determine a candidate's fit to a position during / after the interview? Please elaborate your answer.” answers were different. Some of the HR employees do not participate in the job interview. However, the ones who do mentioned that they look at several things, such as: whether the person fits with the company, if the person is enthusiastic, based on the questions answered, their behavior during the interview and motivation. Roughly 23% of the survey participants mentioned that they do not encounter problems to determine whether a candidate is suited for a job position. However, 77% did mentioned they do encounter problems determining whether a candidate is well suited for a job application. They mentioned that it is a personal decision. Furthermore, 77% mentioned that business intelligence could support decisive

making processes of selection & recruitment. Whilst, 23% mentioned that they do not see potential in business intelligence. For the question how business intelligence can help, they replied all differently. Some mentioned that candidates should make a test, others mentioned that BI can make predictions based on historical data of a candidate and BI could make it more insightful if candidates match with a job position.. Others mentioned that they do not have an answer for this.

Discussion

There are multiple methods for BI tools to be utilised to reduce strain in decision-making processes. Tanila, Umma, Azad & Adnan (2018), for example, suggest implementing such technology to scan CV's of past and present employees, as well as those of candidates and applicants, to identify the key characteristics leading to a successful hire, reducing decision-making strains in a critical HR task (Bhatia, 2013). This information can then be intelligently analysed and presented to a recruiter, showing high-potential candidates to prioritise. Other papers have identified similar uses for BI in the recruitment process; Mishra & Garg (2015) point out the advantages BI could have by analysing the company's “effectiveness of recruitment sources or the time required to successfully fill job openings”, determining the organisation's success rates at employee acquisition and retention. Moreover, BI implementations could aid HR as a whole through several types of analyses, including but not limited to the employee qualification analysis, workforce planning analytics and training & education analytics. The given examples, both affecting recruitment, provide scenarios for one of many subjective decision-making processes within an organisation.

However, the same research papers also point out the severe limitations that currently strain the growth of BI in HR, if not in subjective decision making altogether. Most relevant of all, there would be major technological, infrastructural, training and skilled resource limitations - which would have to be adapted to new working systems (Mishra & Garg, 2015). For example, recruiters would require training in using BI systems in their workflow, along with being skilled with technology already. Moreover, not all employees would be willing to adapt to such changes, causing a segregation of the workforce (Wittig, 2012). Mishra & Garg suggest to alleviate these problems by monitoring and analysing the BI measures which improve decisions and actions, which in turn

requires the identification of the correct metrics to measure. Furthermore, it would require a full collaborative effort between the decision-making team, finance and IT, with significant input from all related line managers and executives. Along with this, the decision-makers would require IT and quantitative skills, and a strong communication and change of management-plan is needed so that an analytics-encouraging culture is created (Mishra & Garg, 2015).

Connecting the aforementioned literature to the survey results, it becomes apparent that there is much room for improvement in recruitment. A majority of the HR specialists surveyed experience inefficiencies or problems when determining the suitability of a candidate to the position they are recruiting for; an issue that the mentioned BI tools could alleviate. 69% of the respondents agree with this: they believe that BI could indeed be of help in their work. This information serves as evidence for BI being in demand in HRM, specialists indeed see a problem that could be solved through the use of intelligent analytical tools. Some respondents go further in-depth, stating “through the lack of information, good candidates could get rejected. By gaining an efficient, computerized source, the occurrence of this will diminish.” and “data is knowledge! Now I make my decisions for a large portion on intuition and I'm only human so mistakes can be easily made.” These responses are in line with the aforementioned literature, demonstrating the need for BI in recruitment.

Conclusion

First of all, with the findings described, it can be concluded that the application of BI in subjective decision-making processes can have added value. This is due to the fact that more than two-thirds of the respondents believe that the application of BI can help with this. However, the conclusion remains that it can contribute and not that it will contribute because of the small number ($n = 16$) respondents within this study. Due to the low number of respondents and the short time span of the study (about six weeks), the researchers also do not see enough support to be able to answer the main research question. However, conducting the research has offered new insights that will emerge later in this chapter as suggestions for further research.

It has been established in the methodology that the first two sub-questions are mainly theoretical in nature and that the last sub-question will be examined on the basis of a survey. The desk research has had a reliable and valid result despite

the limited time for the investigation. However, the external validity of the survey results cannot be guaranteed due to the low number of respondents and the sampling method chosen. The intended number of respondents was (after distribution by the first-grade recipients) set at 30 in order to get a normal distribution in the answers. However, this was lower to 16. In addition, the sampling method chosen (snowball sampling) in which the first-degree respondents (who receive the survey directly from the researchers) further spread is one that is difficult to generalize. As a result, the survey is distributed within one or more specific fields. In our case, these were the IT and logistics sector. The advantage of this is that we see a trend in the differences in outflow percentage between these two fields. The same applies to the fact that the educational requirement differs for both respondent groups, which the difference may also have to do with. Furthermore, we can conclude that we do not have enough evidence to reject the null-hypothesis. This means that we do not have enough evidence that data warehousing has a significant impact on the subjective decision making of HR.

This brings us to the recommendations as a result of new insights. The application of BI in subjective decision-making is a study that is comprehensive in which it is also possible to zoom in on the application of BI in certain sectors / fields of study, where there is a high demand for this, such as the operational logistics sector where a high outflow rate is experienced and a relatively low training requirement applies compared to the IT sector with higher educated people and a lower outflow percentage. In addition, the result that HR personnel do not want to relinquish all authority is an interesting issue for a follow-up investigation. The knowledge gap would then be an application of robotisation and the result of this on employee satisfaction. Here it can be investigated to what extent employees are open to the acceptance of similar technologies that pose a threat to their job.

<https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-59904-883-3.ch034>

Dias, I., & Sousa, M. J. (2015). Business Intelligence Applied to Human Resources Management. *New Contributions in Information Systems and Technologies*, 105–113. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-16528-8_11

Garg, S., & Mishra, R. (2015). Business Intelligence in HR: An Analysis. *ABS International Journal of Management*, 1(3), 59–62. Retrieved from https://test.abs.edu.in/wp-content/uploads/2014/03/abs_journal_vol1_issue3_aug_2015.pdf#page=61

Jones, D. A., Willness, C., & Macneil, S. (2009). Corporate Social Responsibility And Recruitment: Testing Person-organization Fit And Signaling Mechanisms. *Academy of Management Proceedings*, 2009(1), 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.5465/ambpp.2009.44265576>

Kapoor, B. (2010). *Business Intelligence and Its Use for Human Resource Management* (Vol. 6, Num. 2). <http://www.hraljournal.com/Page/3%20Bhushan%20Kapoor.pdf>

Mosavi, A. (2013). TOWARDS AN APPROACH FOR EFFECTIVELY USING INTUITION IN LARGE-SCALE DECISION-MAKING PROBLEMS. Obuda University. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.2567.9125>

Sayegh, L., Anthony, W. P., & Perrewé, P. L. (2004). Managerial decision-making under crisis: The role of emotion in an intuitive decision process. *Human Resource Management Review*, 14(2), 179–199. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrmr.2004.05.002>

Tanila, Umma & Azad, Asma & Adnan, Atm. (2018). Business Intelligence and Databases; An Empirical Study On Its Application Towards Recruitment Process. *Journal for Studies in Management and Planning*. 04. 73-88.

Timar, D. B., & Balas, V. E. (2007). Decision-Making in Human Resources Selection Methodology. *2007 2nd International Workshop on Soft Computing Applications*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/SOFA.2007.4318316>

Watson, H. J., & Wixom, B. H. (2007). The Current State of Business Intelligence. *Computer*, 40(9), 96–99. <https://doi.org/10.1109/mc.2007.331>

Wittig, C. (2012). Employees' Reactions to Organizational Change. *OD PRACTITIONER*, 44(2), 23–28. Retrieved from <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/3136/96331e181fd>

REFERENCES (ALPHABETIC)

Azeroual, O., & Theel, H. (2018). The Effects of Using Business Intelligence Systems on an Excellence Management and Decision-Making Process by Start-Up Companies: A Case Study. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF MANAGEMENT SCIENCE AND BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION*, 4(3), 30–40. <https://doi.org/10.18775/ijmsba.1849-5664-5419.2014.43.1004>

Bhatia, T. (2013). *Recruitment and selection – The most important HR function - Empxtrack*. <https://empxtrack.com/blog/recruitment-and-selecti-on-the-most-important-hr-function/>

Burgard, M., & Piazza, F. (2009). Data Warehouse and Business Intelligence Systems in the Context of E-HRM. *Encyclopedia of Human Resources Information Systems*, 223–229.

[743106f91d9483a77d27686bf.pdf](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-0394.2006.00416.x)

Zhang, L., & Wang, H. (2006). Intelligent information processing in human resource management: an implementation case in China. *Expert Systems*, 23(5), 356–369.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-0394.2006.00416.x>

Question 3: Are you experiencing a high employee turnover (uitstroompercentage) in the sector you are recruiting for? (Yes/No)

Question 4: Where in the recruitment process do you make decisions supported by information systems (business intelligence)? Please elaborate your answer.

Question 5: Where in the recruitment process do you make decisions based on your intuition / subjectivity? Please elaborate your answer.

Question 6: In what way do you determine a candidate's fit to a position prior to the interview? Please elaborate your answer.

Question 7: In what way do you determine a candidate's fit to a position during / after the interview? Please elaborate your answer.

Question 8: Do you experience problems / inefficiencies in determining whether a candidate is suited for the position?

Question 9: Could the use of computerized data (business intelligence) support you in these decision making processes? (Answer: Yes/No)

Question 10: If yes, how?

Appendix A: The survey

The survey that we sent to multiple people is based off of eight questions in total.

Question 1: Does your working position involve recruiting and selecting candidates for vacant positions? (open-ended question)

Question 2: In what industry are you professionally involved? (Nominal categories answers: Logistics, IT, other etc.)